

This supplement reports the complete numerical output from the full factorial Cumulative Link Mixed Models (CLMMs) summarized in Section 4.3 of the main paper. The models were fit on three primary ordinal outcomes (perceived effectiveness, perceived practicality, and willingness to use) using a cumulative logit link and symmetric thresholds in the `ordinal` R package (`c1mm` function), with standard errors derived from the observed Hessian. Each model included outcome (accepted vs. declined) \times device context \times negotiation strategy as fully-crossed fixed effects with a random intercept by participant ($N = 400$ participants \times 3 storyboards = 1200 observations).

Table 1. Model fit diagnostics for the full factorial CLMM.

Dependent variable	N obs	N pid	LogLik	AIC	BIC	Max grad	Random SD
Effectiveness	1200	400	-1398.33	2848.66	2981.00	0.00156	0.849
Practicality	1200	400	-1290.85	2633.69	2766.03	0.00035	1.301
Willingness	1200	400	-1479.15	3010.31	3142.65	0.00071	1.134

Table 2. Threshold parameter estimates. The symmetric parameterization estimates a central location and a spacing parameter; the three implied response-category thresholds ($\theta_{k|k+1}$) are derived.

Dependent variable	Central		Spacing		Derived thresholds		
	Est.	SE	Est.	SE	$\theta_{1 2}$	$\theta_{2 3}$	$\theta_{3 4}$
Effectiveness	-0.586	0.300	1.676	0.071	-2.262	-0.586	1.091
Practicality	0.847	0.328	2.265	0.096	-1.418	0.847	3.112
Willingness	-0.295	0.310	1.710	0.071	-2.004	-0.295	1.415

Table 3. Type II likelihood-ratio tests for fixed effects. Boldface indicates $p < .05$.

Term	df	Effectiveness		Practicality		Willingness	
		χ^2	p	χ^2	p	χ^2	p
outcome	1	383.65	<.001	199.47	<.001	156.03	<.001
context	2	77.27	<.001	22.04	<.001	13.30	.001
strategy	3	70.67	<.001	19.95	<.001	43.19	<.001
outcome \times context	2	2.14	.343	1.79	.409	6.37	.041
outcome \times strategy	3	3.29	.349	4.40	.222	4.05	.256
context \times strategy	6	13.40	.037	12.85	.045	5.50	.482
outcome \times context \times strategy	6	15.52	.017	7.68	.262	10.32	.112